

FLOSS Live Coding

Live coding for VJ, Algorave & Shader-Showdowns & Jams

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FLOSS Live Coding

Colophon

title: FLOSS Live Coding

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tags: Rave, Live, AlgoRave, VJ, ShaderShowdown

description: Mostly FLOSS Collection of some stuff around Live Coding, Algorave, Sha

Why?

Just experienced [Lynn Drumm's DJ-Set @ Revision25](#) set with 38(!) live coders all over the world in a shader jam. Unbelievable! It was a mega crazy mind-blowing milestone in the livecoding area. So I just want to check out what tools, apps, and bits and pieces are used to make stuff like this happen.

Stuff for Live coding, VJ, Algorave & Shader Showdown & Jams

Live Coding Audio

1. [TidalCycles](#) Pattern-based Haskell DSL for live music
2. [Strudel](#) JS port for Tidal. It's like codepen for algoraving.
3. [FoxDot](#) Python live coding for SuperCollider
4. [SuperCollider](#) Audio synthesis & programming language
5. [Sonic Pi](#) Ruby-based live music platform (ideal for education)
6. [ORCA](#) Esoteric ASCII live coding sequencer
7. [Gibber / Gibberwocky](#) Browser-based music & visuals with JS
8. [Hydra](#) Web-based, audio-reactive visuals by Olivia Jack

Live Coding Video

1. [Bonzomatic](#) Real-time shader live coding with GLSL
2. [Bonzomatic \(0b5er Fork\)](#) Extended fork with audio sync, multi-pass, etc.
3. [ShaderToy \(modded\)](#) Custom versions with MIDI, audio, etc.
4. [ISF \(Interactive Shader Format\)](#) Shaders for VDMX & Co
5. [TouchDesigner](#) Modular real-time visual builder
6. [VDMX](#) (\$) Mac-based VJ platform with ISF, audio reactivity
7. [Resolume](#) (\$) Standard VJ software for club visuals
8. [Notch](#) (\$) High-end real-time visuals for stage & events
9. [OpenFrameworks](#) C++ framework for creative real-time applications
10. [Processing / p5.js](#) Java/JavaScript frameworks for generative art
11. [ISF \(Interactive Shader Format\)](#) Official GitHub page of the ISF project by Vidvox.

Sync & Communication

1. [OSC \(Open Sound Control\)](#) Network communication for audio & visuals
2. [MIDI](#) Classic trigger & sync standard
3. [Ableton Link](#) (\$) BPM/beat sync across multiple tools
4. [FFT Analysis](#) Frequency analysis as a control signal
5. [Syphon](#) Video sharing between VJ apps (Mac/Win)
6. [Spout](#) - ...
7. [flok](#) great multiuser live coding editor

Communities

1. [TOPLAP](#) International live coding community & philosophy
2. [Algorave.org](#) Home base of the algorave movement
3. [Demozoo](#) Database & archive of all demoscene releases
4. [Demoparty.net](#) Directory of all demo scene events worldwide
5. [livecode.demozoo.org](#) Shader Showdown database
6. [Pouët](#) Classic demo scene platform & forum for releases
7. [Revision Party](#) Official website of the largest demo scene party
8. [the.CodingTrain](#) Tutorials & inspiration for generative coding
9. [glsandbox.com](#) Community-based WebGL shader platform
10. [Patchstorage](#) Collection of patches for TouchDesigner, Hydra, VDMX
11. [Algorave India](#) - Nice community, with learning stuff, for e.g. strudel guide

Extras & Experiments

1. [Cables.gl](#) Node-based WebGL visual patching in the browser
2. [vvv gamma](#) Visual real-time programming tool
3. [Max/MSP / Jitter](#) Classic for interactive audio-visual art
4. [OBS + Shader Plugins](#) Livestreaming + real-time effects
5. [All things live coding](#) A l-o-o-o-ng list